

Topic detection in COVID-19 mortality time series

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Abstract. The mortality of COVID-19 has been analyzed from a predictive point of view, building models that failed to predict the medium and long term evolution of the time series. Looked in a retrospective way, it is possible to appreciate that the mortality impact of the pandemic was very different across countries. In this paper we deal with the discovery of representative patterns, i.e. topics in latent Dirichlet analysis (LDA), that may explain the observed mortality time series. The choice of the number of topics is a balance between the minimization of perplexity, and the avoidance of overfitting. We find that countries can be clustered according to the coefficients of the decomposition of their time series into topics, and that this decomposition has a geopolitical correspondence, i.e. countries with the same dominant topic representation belong to the same geographical and/or political domain.

1 Introduction

Out of the hundreds of thousands of papers published somehow related with COVID-19 pandemic, those dealing with Machine Learning and like predictive approaches were mostly dealing with predicting the individual patient risks for severe disease [4]. Most epidemiological works, have focused on the prediction of the number cases applying epidemiological models [7], classical statistical tools as well as Machine Learning and Deep Learning tools [1].

Why focus on mortality time series? While number of cases reported maybe heavily influenced by the testing pressure, the political decisions about who is to be tested more frequently, and the quality of the testing materials, procedures, and even personnel qualifications, the deaths attributed to COVID-19 have less confusing factors and appear to be a more rigorous account of the pandemic impact on the society. The only confusing factor seems to be whether the death was due to COVID-19 or COVID-19 was detected while the person was about to die from other causes. This confusion was a key issue during the Omicron wave [5].

In this paper we do not try to make any kind of extrapolation of the data, such as the prediction of the actual death toll of the pandemic by means of regression methods [3]. In fact, we do not question the published data, taking it at face value. In other words, we think that across the world all governments are clever enough to count deaths. Instead, we look for patterns of the mortality

across countries that give an indirect picture of the diversity of circumstances and responses to the pandemic. To this end, we apply latent Dirichlet analysis (LDA) in order to extract latent templates of mortality time series. The decomposition (or explanation) of each country COVID-19 mortality time series into these templates should allow to find clusters of similar countries and to appreciate the dissimilarity among the countries belonging to different clusters.

The underlying hypothesis of the pandemic response is that there is a single well isolated and identified pathogen as the cause and that there is only one feasible strategy to cope with it, namely vaccination and social control measures. In other words, because the pathogen is unique the treatment should be the same for everybody. However, any casual inspection finds quite diverse results in terms of mortality time series patterns under a rather uniform set of measures taken by governments across the world that appear to contradict this hypothesis. Our ongoing work discovers underlying patterns of mortality and their spatial distributions of their expression that would allow to look for underlying causes for the diversity focusing on the actual policies implemented in the countries.

2 Materials and Methods

The code and data are published in zenodo¹ as well as figures and future versions of this work as long as it is evolving.

2.1 Our world in data

“Our world in data” (OWID) is a web site devoted to the publication of relevant data for the pressing geopolitical and economic questions. It is hosted by the University of Oxford and has been extensively funded by Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, thus it is not suspicious of being on the side of the conspiracy theorists. OWID has been publishing relevant data for the follow up of COVID-19 pandemic², aggregating it from several sources. Mortality time series were taken from the John Hopkins COVID-19 site until march 2023, when it stopped updating data after the WHO published the end of the pandemic and most countries stopped reporting. For this work, we have taken the dataset as published on the first days of 2023, which we think covers the pandemic evolution. We consider the seven day rolling average time series, to avoid artifacts due to reporting irregularities, such as zero deaths in weekends.

2.2 Latent Dirichlet Analysis

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) [2] is a technique originally proposed for population genetics analysis [8] which has extensively been used for natural language processing. LDA aims to discover the latent topics $T = \{t_i\}_{i=1}^K$ underlying a set of documents $D = \{d_i\}_{i=1}^M$ and to explain the documents in terms

¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10403170>

² <https://ourworldindata.org/explorers/coronavirus-data-explorer>

of these topics. The documents are characterized by a vectorial representation $d_i = [c_{j,i}]_{j=1}^V$ where each vector entry is a counter of the number of appearances in the document of the corresponding word in a vocabulary $V = \{w_i\}_{i=1}^V$. Thus the dimension of the vector representation is the size of the vocabulary. Each topic is defined by the vector of probabilities of appearances of the vocabulary words in the topic $t_i = [\varphi_{j,i}]_{j=1}^V$ s.t. $\sum_j \varphi_{j,i} = 1$. The explanation of the documents in terms of topics $E = \{e_i\}_{i=1}^M$ is given by the probability of appearance of the topic in the document $e_i = [\theta_{j,i}]_{j=1}^K$ s.t. $\sum_j \theta_{j,i} = 1$, i.e. by a mixture of topics. The model assumes that topic mixtures and the topics follow a Dirichlet distribution of parameters α and β , respectively. Given the set of topics T , LDA assumes a generative process, where first a topic mixture is sampled from Dirichlet distribution $e \sim \text{Dirichlet}(\alpha)$, then each word in the document is generated in a two step process: firstly a topic $z \in T$ is selected following the discrete distribution given by e , secondly, a word $w \in V$ from the vocabulary is selected according to the discrete distribution given by t_z . The induction of the latent topics can be done by several approaches. In this work, we have used the collapsed Gibbs sampling [6] which is the default matlab solver.

In order to determine an good number of topics (we avoid the term 'optimal' because we only partly used a cost function minimum in the decision) we have carried out a grid search on the number of topics between 3 and 40 topics looking for the minimum perplexity of the model explaining the training data. We did not split into training and validation because of the small sample size (the number of countries). Besides, we consider the ratio between the sample size and the number of topics, discarding perplexity minima for high values of this ratio, which we interpret as a predictor of overfitting.

In our work, documents are equated to the mortality time series of each country, words correspond to date, and the word counts are the number of death reported each day. Therefore, the topics correspond to the distribution of death probabilities along the time span considered, which is a value proportional to the mortality rate per day. Topics provide the qualitative shapes of prototypical mortality time series explaining the actual observed mortality time series. Interpretations of topics and their relation to the causes of mortality are outside the scope of the paper.

2.3 tSNE

We apply t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) [9] in order to visualize in 2D the high dimensional topic mixtures explaining each country time series. This visualization allows to assess qualitatively the aggregation of country time series into clusters. In short, t-SNE models the conditional probabilities of two data samples being neighbors in the original space and the projection space, which in our case is 2D. Then it tries to find the best localizations of the points in 2D by minimizing a Kullback-Leibler divergence by gradient descent. The formulation of this divergence is built up assuming that the distribution of

distances among vector features in the original space is Gaussian, while in the visualization space it is a t-Student.

3 Results

Fig. 1. The search for the number of topics with minimal perplexity

Figure 1 shows the result of our search for an optimal number of topics minimizing perplexity of the modeling of the dataset. We found some local minima over 20 topics, but we consider that the ratio of the number of topics to the sample size is too high, leading to overfitting, so we selected $K=14$ as a good number of topics. Figure 2 plots the topics induced by LDA from the data. Each plot is a probability distribution, hence the values are very low, but we are interested in the shapes of the time series, specifically the occurrence of waves of maximal probability of death. Figure 3 shows the correlation among the topics plotted previously. High correlation means that topics may be redundant. It can be appreciated that most topics are uncorrelated, which can be interpreted as a good basis for representation of country mortality time series. Figure 4 shows the decomposition of countries time series into topics plotting the mixture probabilities. This figure has the limitation that some topics have the same color due to software limitations. Many countries have a largely dominant topic, meaning that they follow closely the mortality in time template. Some countries have a more uniform distribution among a small number of topics. Figure 5 shows the 2D visualization of the sample achieved by t-SNE. It is apparent that there are some very well differentiated clusters of countries that share similar mixtures of topics. Figure 6 encodes each country according to its more probable topic. It can be appreciated that there are some regions of the world where countries share similar codes. It is prominent that western Europe and North America

Fig. 2. The 14 topics uncovered by LDA

Fig. 3. Correlations among topics

seem to belong to the same cluster. Easter European countries shape another region, while Russia and some of its neighbors shape another. From this figure, it is clear that similar policies enforced by countries sharing a political view and some geographical features shaped the mortality results of the pandemic.

4 Discussion

From the point of view of the diversity of country mortality patterns, Figure 2 provides some key insights. Topics #6 and #7 have big waves in spring 2020, corresponding to western European countries (with the exception of Portugal) and North America. Topic #6 has an Omicron wave, and the shapes of these topics at the beginning of the vaccination campaign have small differences. Topic #5 and #12, on the other hand, have first wave in the middle of the year 2020, summer in the northern hemisphere, winter in the southern hemisphere. In fact these topics are presented in South America and Africa, suggesting a seasonal effect in the virus, which later disappeared. Omicron wave was almost synchronous across the globe, regardless of hemisphere. Topic #8 shows a very late presentation of mortality, after entire populations were vaccinated. This topic was dominant in New Zealand, which enforced a strict zero covid policy. China is a special case in our study, because our data stops in the first days of 2023, before the explosion of cases and deaths that happened in the first months of the year after the Chinese government relaxed the zero covid policies.

Figure 6 provides a spatial interpretation key. Some countries, such as western Europe countries minus Portugal have very similar mortality time series patterns after enforcing rather similar policies. USA and Canada have similar response patterns to western Europe, though the absolute and relative count of deaths are

Fig. 4. Decomposition of countries mortality time series into detected topics

Fig. 5. Clusters of countries visualized by the tSNE 2D embedding of the countries decomposition into topics. Topic identification corresponds to the topic with maximal probability for a country.

Map of topics per country

Fig. 6. Geographical location of topics

rather different between Canada and USA. Apparently, the modulation of the final count of deaths over the time series templates is dependent of additional factors, which may be climatic or other underlying cultural, genetic or ethnic. For instance, the USA suffers an epidemic of obesity [10] and diabetes mellitus [11] which may be responsible for the extraordinary death toll of the pandemic. The case of Portugal is to be highlighted because it shows the differential impact of policies with its only neighboring country, specially during the first wave of spring 2020.

If examine the clusters of countries in Figure 5 we find that some topics show some concentrated clusters with sparse outliers far from the them. Topic #1, for instance, appears in two separate clusters. This can correspond to countries with 'pure' topic #1, where its probability is almost one versus countries with a more uniform distribution of topics where topic #1 is 'by chance' the dominant one. This is an explanation for the appearance of this topic in quite diverse regions of the world.

5 Conclusions

We have carried out a latent topic detection that unveils some patterns of mortality time series explaining the observed mortality time series as a linear composition of such templates. Consideration of these explanations as feature vectors describing each country allows to detect clusters of countries with similar time series that have either geographical similarities or underlying sociopolitical affinities, or both.

Future works may consider additional measures for the determination of a good number of topics, such as avoiding the occurrence of highly correlated pairs of topics. More independent topics may lead to more parsimonious improved decompositions of mortality time series into mixtures of topics. Another line of work consists of exploring other feature extraction processes, such as Principal Component Analysis, Independent Component Analysis, or Non Negative Matrix Factorization.

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